

D3.3 Integration of Critical Assessment of Practices

28 February 2025 (v9)

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Table 1. The SINCRONY Consortium

	Name of the Entity	Acronym	Role	Country	ORG Type
1	Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna	UNIBO	CO	IT	RTD
2	Universidade do Porto	U. PORTO	BE	PT	RTD
3	Association Européenne pour la Démocratie Locale	ALDA	BE	FR	NGO
4	WeDo Project Intelligence Made Easy SL	WeDo	BE	ES	SME
5	Aalborg Universitet	AAU	BE	DK	RTD
6	Turun Yliopisto	UTU	BE	FI	RTD
7	Universitaet Innsbruck	UIBK	BE	AT	RTD
8	Université de Genève	UNIGE	AP	CH	RTD
9	The University of Manchester	UNIMAN	AP	UK	RTD

*Legend = Role in the Project: C – Coordinator // B – Beneficiary // AP – Associated Partner // Organization Type: RTD – Research and Technological Development// PHI – Public Health Institution // Hosp – Hospital // SME – Small and medium-sized enterprises. // LC – Large Company // NGO – Non-Governmental Org.

Table 2. The SINCRONY Work Packages

	Work Packages Name	WP Leader
WP1	Coordination and Management	UNIBO
WP2	Co-Design	UNIBO
WP3	Assessment of existing practices in an intersectional lens	UTU
WP4	Power-based analysis of social narratives and experiences	UNIGE
WP5	Piloting enhancement and innovation pathways	ALDA
WP6	Evaluation	U. PORTO
WP7	Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation, and Impact	WeDo

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report integrates the key findings of the critical assessments of youth deliberative and participatory practices at EU-level and at national and local levels. In the former case, these findings emerge from the assessment of 20 EU-level projects. In the latter, the practices analysed were taken from 25 educational and 50 organisational settings in five countries (Denmark, Finland, Italy, Portugal and the UK).

Drawing on the critical analysis of practices across national settings and sectors (community organisations, local authorities, educational settings) as well as different types of projects and programmes, in this report the criteria used to identify good practice are integrated. The integrated set of criteria retain their focus on inclusivity and intersectionality but are revised to ensure they facilitate assessment of the substance rather than description of practices. For example, the criteria are designed to identify practices that recognise and work to tackle inequalities arising from overlapping identities, not whether or not the practice discusses this through the language of intersectional inequality.

Applying these integrated criteria, a range of examples of good practice for each of the criteria and sub-criteria are identified. These examples are drawn from the practices studied and are presented together with publicly available source references where more information can be found. Examples of good practice to include in the report have been selected with the aim of including as wide a range as possible in terms of the sector, level (EU, national, local), type of project or organisation, and national context.

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Table 1 Integrated Criteria

1. INTRODUCTION

The critical assessment of deliberative and participatory practices at EU and at national/local levels identified a number of key factors, which have shaped the work to integrate assessment criteria and recommend examples of good practice to be included in the footprint calculator and toolkits for working with schools and organisations.

The first is that the context of good practice often shapes how it is presented or referred to. For example, recognition of intersectional inclusion or the limits to deliberative practice without structural change may not be explicit either because practices need to be described in accessible language or because the practices take place in formal settings – for example, schools – which constrain the degree to which power structures are open to challenge. Secondly, while external assessment of practices may appear to be the gold standard, the statutory and cultural context of practices differs significantly across countries and sectors. Self-assessment has the advantage of ensuring these local cultural factors are taken into account – for example, a good practice may not be cited in documentation available to external assessors because it is routine (or even obligatory) in some contexts. Offering self-assessment as a baseline for schools and organisations to benchmark their existing practices thus has some distinct advantages. However, critical reflection also revealed that particular attention is needed to ensure that such assessment does not penalise organisations where good practice is already routinised or even mandatory. For example, in some national contexts, the establishment of youth councils is mandatory (or almost universal even if not obligatory) in educational and local authority settings. Where this is the case, the value of such practices may be underplayed or even appear to go against good practice (for example with regard to the criterion of youth participation being ‘voluntary’). Thus, more nuanced questions need to be asked to ascertain how participation is inclusive, democratic and recognised even where it is mandatory. Thirdly, these national and cultural nuances extend to different models underpinning youth voice strategies which may be rooted either in traditional (Habermasian) modes of deliberation emphasising discussion and agreement or in more radical empowerment approaches. An assessment framework must take into account a variety of approaches and not prioritise a single model.

A related concern identified whilst conducting the initial critical assessments relates to the wide range of entities that may want to employ the footprint calculator to assess their practices. At national and local levels, these may include very different types of organisations such as non-profit community organisations, charities or social enterprises, youth voice projects or services delivered by, or directly funded by, local councils or municipal authorities, umbrella or national youth organisations, individual schools (including independent, fee-paying schools) or educational trusts and projects implemented across a number of schools funded by national or local government or international organisations. At EU level, projects and programmes with very different core functions may seek to benchmark activity in this way including those that are primarily research focused, those engaging in training or education (e.g. through citizen science approaches), those seeking to directly engage young people in institutions or forums of European Union governance, or those promoting networking, capacity building or social activism. Such practices also differ significantly in terms of types of provision ranging from one-off ‘flagship’ projects to long-established youth or student councils that function as part of the everyday

school, organisation or local authority governance structure. In developing the footprint calculator, it is essential that the tool can be used by as wide a range of entities as possible. This might be facilitated, for example, by making the calculator modular, allowing different organisations to self-assess on those elements central to their activities. Or, conversely, to explore those elements that they perhaps had not previously considered. It is also essential that it reflects the different contributions made by both short-term and long-term youth voice action programmes.

2. INTEGRATING EU AND NATIONAL/LOCAL LEVEL CRITERIA

The first step towards integrating the critical assessment of practices facilitating young people's participation and deliberation was to generate an integrated set of assessment criteria. When conducting the EU level analysis and the national/local level analysis, the criteria used for each were generated inductively (through pilot coding of a small number of cases) and then matched against the extant academic and practice literature. The researchers then compared the two sets of criteria and adjusted the two lists so that, although not identical, both sets of criteria were broadly in line and would allow subsequent integration. For the EU level analysis, four main criteria were used: external inclusion, internal inclusion, intersectional purpose, and output. For the National/Local level analysis, six main criteria were employed: inclusion; participation; deliberation; intersectionality; recognition; and influence. Within each category, sub-criteria were also employed. This process, and the criteria and sub-criteria used in each case, are described in detail in Huttunen et al. (2024) and Mirshak and Pilkington (2024) respectively.

In shaping a single, integrated set of criteria (see Table 1), we drew on our critical reflections from the earlier analyses (as briefly outlined in the Introduction) as well as the key objective that the integrated criteria could be used in the development of the footprint calculator. Central to this was that the integrated criteria were applicable to a wide range of practices and users including educational institutions, NGOs, umbrella youth organisations, local authority departments, policy makers and young people active in youth councils or organisations. Secondly, we wanted to generate criteria that could be used not for external evaluation, but for benchmarking current practices in terms of their inclusivity and intersectional awareness through a **critical self-assessment** process. Thirdly, we wanted to maximise the potential usefulness of the footprint calculator by avoiding academic or politically (particular approach-centred) language. Finally, we wanted to ensure that the calculator not only provided an indication of how well an organisation was doing against particular markers, but offered users examples of good practice that might help develop existing, or introduce new, practices. Thus, against each criteria and sub-criteria, we identified questions that could be potentially asked of the practice such that users could answer 'yes', 'no' or 'partially' as to whether their practice is characterised by this quality. The good practice examples detailed in Section 3 can then be used within the footprint calculator to provide users with ideas and suggestions for further development.

Table 1 Integrated Criteria

Criteria		Questions for self-assessment
<p>Inclusion</p>	<p>1.1 Recruitment</p>	<p>Are there any formal exclusions to participation in activities e.g. based on nationality, citizenship or age? If so, are these exclusions required by an external agency [e.g. funder, legal institution, local authority, national government]?</p> <p>Are young people recruited through self-selection [do they put themselves forward for participation]?</p> <p>Are young people recruited through open invitation that reaches all sections of society?</p> <p>Are young people recruited through random sampling [or similar direct approach that avoids self-selection]?</p> <p>Are young people recruited as representatives via election or selection?</p> <p>If representatives are (s)elected, do all those they will represent have the opportunity to (s)elect them?</p>
	<p>1.2 Proactive inclusion</p>	<p>Are efforts made to reach out to marginalised youth or those who would not put themselves forward?</p> <p>When reaching out to young people, are efforts made to encourage participation of people with diverse gender, class or sexual identities and different racial, ethnic or migration backgrounds?</p> <p>Are efforts made to reach those with different (dis)abilities?</p>
	<p>1.3 Accessibility</p>	<p>Are spaces (physical or virtual) of participation accessible for those with additional needs?</p> <p>Has everything possible been done to mitigate any accessibility issues due to constraints of the space or venue?</p> <p>Is plain language used in information about recruitment and activities?</p> <p>Is language interpretation available for those who need it in order to participate?</p> <p>Are costs of the participation (travel, accommodation, equipment) borne by the organiser not the participant?</p>
	<p>1.4 Belonging</p>	<p>Are efforts made to ensure young people feel they 'belong' in the venue or space?</p> <p>Is the venue or space provided comfortable, welcoming and safe for young people?</p> <p>Are efforts made to ensure participants do not feel excluded due to their age, (dis)ability, or identity characteristics (such as class, gender, sexuality, ethnic, racial or migration background)?</p>
	<p>1.5 Support</p>	<p>Is training provided to enable participation?</p> <p>Is ongoing support provided to enable participation?</p>
<p>2. Voice</p>	<p>2.1 Forms of participation</p>	<p>Are young people engaged through consultation?</p> <p>Are young people included in co-design or co-production of activities?</p> <p>Does participation include embodied and emotional modes of expression (e.g. storytelling, music, dance etc)?</p>

		Are digital technologies and social media employed to facilitate participation?
	2.2 Sites of participation	Are young people able to participate in non-formal, everyday settings? If young people participate in formal sites, do these include places that would otherwise be hard for them to access (e.g. parliament or other institutions of power)?
	2.3 Power and participation	Is participation always voluntary? Is participation young person-led or young person-initiated? Are young people able to set the agenda by bringing their issues into discussion? Are young people seen as political actors or citizens in their own right? If activities are primarily about training for participation, are young people empowered to see themselves as citizens now, not just in the future?
	2.4 Facilitating discussion and deliberation	Are a wide range of voices heard? Are facilitators or moderators employed to ensure equality in participation and/or mutual respect? Are participants encouraged to develop a shared understanding of a social phenomenon as problematic or unjust?
3. Critique	3.1 Exposing and challenging power relations	Does the practice make visible and challenge structural power relations? E.g. does it expose and critique racialised, postcolonial, gendered, classed, heteronormative, ability-centred or age-centred norms that sustain existing hierarchies of power? Is the interwoven nature of structures of power recognised?
	3.2 Extending political agency	Is there sensitivity to the complexity of young people's identities? Is there awareness that different identity factors may compound the exclusion of some young people? Does the practice actively encourage learning from people in marginalised positions? Is the contribution of a broader and more diverse range of participants recognised as vital to improving democracy?
	3.3 Institutional change	Does the practice aim to bring about institutional changes in public, political institutions or schools and organisations? Are the limits of deliberation, without structural change, recognised?
	3.4 Challenging injustice	Does the practice aim to challenge injustice?
4. Recognition	4.1 Acknowledgement	Is participation publicly acknowledged? Is young people's voice accorded respect?
	4.2 Reward	Is participation remunerated (paid)? Is participation recognised in a non-monetary way (e.g. accreditation, certification, awards, publicity)?

		Do participants gain expert knowledge or training during the practice? If so, is this knowledge or skill accredited or certified?
5. Impact	5.1 Impact objectives	Does young people's voice contribute to decision making? Are explicit recommendations made in order to achieve a policy impact?
	5.2 Stated impact	Are the impacts of policy recommendations, project or activities made public? Are concrete examples or case studies of how young people's voice is listened to made public?
	5.3 Monitoring and assessing impact	Is there a system for monitoring and evidencing impact of the practice? Is the impact resulting from participation fed back to young people? Has the practice or project been formally assessed? Are the results of the assessment made public? Is learning from the assessment detailed?

3 GOOD PRACTICE EXAMPLES

Good practice examples, drawn from the EU-level and national/local analyses of youth deliberative and participatory practices (see Huttunen et al., 2024 and Mirshak and Pilkington, 2024), are provided below against each main and sub-criterion.

It should be noted that the first two questions asked within criterion 3.1.1 Recruitment will be used in the footprint calculator to establish whether any formal exclusions to participation are in place and whether the organisation or project relies on self-selection. Presence of these criteria therefore are not considered 'good practice' but there may be logistical reasons for why recruitment is done in this way. Thus, the examples we present on these two questions illustrate awareness of the potential to introduce exclusions unintentionally in a project design or reflection on how to mitigate outcomes of self-selection by targeting a broad range of potential participants. For similar reasons, the first two questions within criterion 3.2.1 Forms of participation are combined for the purposes of providing good practice examples. Thus, the footprint calculator will filter first for whether young people are engaged only through consultation and then ask about the presence of co-production or co-design. For the purposes of providing good practice examples, however, the question here asks only for forms of engagement that go beyond consultation.

3.1 Inclusion

3.1.1 Recruitment

Are there any formal exclusions to participation in activities e.g. based on nationality, citizenship or age? If so, are these exclusions required by an external agency (e.g. funder, legal institution, local authority, national government)?

While formal exclusions of young people from participation may be due to specific criteria of a programme such as age, education or living in a certain locality, SALTO warns against embedding unintended exclusion into a project's design. For example, if a project's activities take place on Saturdays, they might exclude young Jewish people who observe the Shabbat. A project might also exclude neurodiverse young people if information about activities is not clear.

<https://participationpool.eu/toolkit/>

Are young people recruited through self-selection (i.e. they put themselves forward for participation)?

Ungdomsøen aims to recruit young people through utilising its existing connections with partners including high schools, the Scouts and the Danish Youth Council. This allows it to target a broad range of youth groups

<https://ungdomsoen.dk/partnere>

Are young people recruited through open invitation that reaches all sections of society?

#IDEAGIOVANI is a project enabling young people to play a leading role in the renewal of a former cinema building in a small municipality in the Modena region. Personal invitations were sent by the local Mayor and other influential public figures to all young people (aged 12 to 24 years) living in the town to encourage participation. More than half of the young people living in the area took part in the first stage of the project.

<https://www.osservatoriopartecipazione.it/scheda-processo/2552>

Are young people recruited through random sampling (or similar method of direct approach that avoids self-selection)?

The WE DO Democracy Youth Citizens' Assembly reached out directly to over 90,000 young people in Copenhagen via e-Boks in an attempt to ensure it was representative. Over 800 young people expressed a desire to participate. The final selection of 26 assembly participants was made using stratified random sampling based on gender, age, education and origin.

<https://www.wedodemocracy.dk/case/naar-unge-stemmer-til-kommunalvalget/>

Are young people recruited as representatives via election or selection? If representatives are (s)elected, do all those who they will represent have the opportunity to (s)elect them?

Students at the Co-op Academy Belle Vue can put themselves forward for leadership positions through a written or video application process. This is followed by a democratic election campaign whereby candidates canvas the student body to vote for them.

<https://www.bellevue.coopacademies.co.uk/page/?title=Student+Leadership&pid=189>

3.1.2 Proactive Inclusion

Are efforts made to reach out to marginalised youth or those who would not put themselves forward?

Wolverhampton City Council's *Children and Young People's Participation and Co-Production Strategy* suggests proactively targeting young people facing the greatest barriers to getting involved. This includes younger children and young people from minority ethnic backgrounds, those living in disadvantaged neighbourhoods, children missing school, young people in the youth justice system, refugees, traveller children and disabled children with special needs.

<https://wolverhampton.moderngov.co.uk/documents/s101710/Appendix%201%20for%20Children%20and%20Young%20Peoples%20Participation%20and%20Co-Production%20Strategy%202019-2021.pdf>

UPLIFT utilises tailor-made strategies to target specific demographics or groups that are difficult to reach and who would not usually put themselves forward. These include snowball recruitment methods.

<https://uplift-youth.b-cdn.net/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/Uplift-policy-brief-3a.pdf>

When reaching out to young people, are efforts made to encourage participation of people with diverse gender, class or sexual identities and different racial, ethnic or migration backgrounds?

Barnardo's targeted search and recruitment efforts are led by people who understand the needs of children and young people from diverse backgrounds and communities, including those who are Black, Minoritised Ethnic, LGBT+ and/or disabled.

<https://www.barnardos.org.uk/sites/default/files/2023-12/Barnardo%27s%20Strategy%202024%20-%202027%20%28FINAL%29.pdf>

Are efforts made to reach those with different (dis)abilities?

SUMH is a Danish umbrella association for youth with disabilities. Its 'Together for the Future' (Fælles om Fritiden) programme aims to engage young people with disabilities in leisure activities and voluntary work. It actively seeks to recruit young disabled people including through videos on its website.

<https://www.xn--flesomfritiden-xlb.dk/stu>

3.1.3 Accessibility

Are spaces (physical or virtual) of participation accessible for those with additional needs?

Lapha! is a virtual game that engages young people to help design local wellbeing services in Lapland, Finland. One of the outcomes was the demand from young people that wellbeing services should be easily accessible to all. They also asked for digital services, including remote therapy, to make them more accessible over a long distance.

<https://lapha.fi/documents/594637/766960/Hyvinvointia%21+pelin+nuorten+julkilausuma+vuonna+2023.pdf>

Participation People 'youth-proofs' its language by incorporating memes, short engaging infographics, and easy-to-read reports co-created with young people to ensure young people's voices are heard and their ideas effectively conveyed.

<https://participationpeople.com/our-impact-report-young-minds-fresh-perspectives-better-business-decisions/>

Has everything possible been done to mitigate any accessibility issues due to constraints of the space or venue for participation?

The Peer Act project brought organisations together to promote non-discrimination among young people in six European countries. The evaluation report notes that the workshops offered a truly inclusive space, providing concrete examples, for example, of how peer trainers adapted activities for wheelchair users.

<https://par.org.pt/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/Evaluation-Report-Peeract.pdf>

Is plain language used in recruitment and activity information?

The Changemaker! Project calls for opportunities to be provided for everyone to participate regardless of their language skills. They instruct those using the exercises in their Democracy Education Guide to be prepared to clarify key concepts. As part of this, plain language must be used and points must be illustrated with images or activities. They also note that the language and concepts used must support equality.

<https://plan.fi/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/Demokratiakasvatuksen-reittiopas-2022.pdf>

Is language interpretation available for those who need it in order to participate?

The Sámi Youth Council makes language interpretation available for its youth representatives, with the costs charged to the council's budget. The minutes of the meetings are written in Finnish, but the Sámi Youth Council activities are also communicated in all Sámi languages.

<https://nuor.fi/fi/nuorisoneuvosto/>

Peer Act translates its training resources in order to ensure that trainers have access to resources in their own language which would enable them to better understand and adapt activities in ways that avoid ethnocentrism and sexism.

<https://par.org.pt/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/Evaluation-Report-Peeract.pdf>

Are costs of the participation (travel, accommodation, equipment) borne by the organiser not the participant?

The Young Mayor project in Santa Maria da Feira provides for the costs of training and capacity building, study visits and other expenses related to the holding of office by the elected mayor.

<https://files.diariodarepublica.pt/2s/2018/01/007000000/0116701170.pdf>

One of the impacts achieved by the Finnish Youth Parliament was to pass a resolution requiring that the travel expenses for student representatives participating in the Youth Parliament would be reimbursed.

<https://www.eduskunta.fi/FI/NuortenEduskunta/NuortenParlamentti/Sivut/mika-on-nuorten-parlamentti.aspx>

3.1.4 Belonging

Are efforts made to ensure young people feel they 'belong' in the venue or space?

The Danish Youth Refugee Council utilises 'Udtaler' (Speakers) to help develop strong communities where young people from refugee backgrounds are able to engage in debates and learn how to influence opinions. Through their engagement, they develop a sense of belonging to that community and the capacity to bring about change.

<https://stemmerudafboksen.dk/udtaler/>

Rapolitics cooperates with the Roskilde music festival - attracting over 130,000 attendees - to offer young people, especially those from minority ethnic backgrounds, an opportunity to feel they belong and have a place through art and creative expression.

<https://www.rapolitics.dk/projekter/re-act>

Is the venue or space provided comfortable, welcoming and safe for young people?

Bytes' *Empathy Programme* commits to creating 'shared, non-judgemental spaces for young people to meet and interact' in order to 'build safer, more inclusive communities'.

<https://www.bytes.org/about/>

Are efforts made to ensure participants do not feel excluded due to their age, (dis)ability, or identity characteristics (such as class, gender, sexuality, ethnic, racial, or migration background)?

The Youth Republic model of student voice at the Lousada Oeste school includes all members of all classes in the School Assembly. The Republic adopts a small group model to facilitate participation among students who struggle to voice their opinions in larger groups. The structure and activities of the project aim to provide comfortable spaces for all students to participate in school decisions and functioning.

https://lousadaoeste.org/index.php?option=com_sppagebuilder&view=page&id=4&Itemid=278

3.1.5 Support

Is training provided to enable participation?

In the Citizen Jury on New Genomic Techniques, young participants learned about the topic from experts in the field to enable them to make informed decisions in line with the general principles of deliberative decision-making.

<https://ssrn.com/abstract=4719681>

In *Our Life, Our Voice*, young participants were trained to collect written evidence from experts and analyse interviews and surveys. They also spoke to professionals, including human rights experts to gain an understanding of the work being done to advocate for and support Roma communities.

https://ourlifeourvoice.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/Docs_Project/documents/InvestigationIntoPoverty.YP.IO1.pdf.pdf

Is ongoing support provided to enable participation?

Anna Freud offers training to all children, young people, parents and carers who work with the charity. This includes leadership training in order to lead on a project or programme delivery. Their young Ambassadors receive ongoing training, which covers training in the Lundy model, skills for ambassadors and media training.

<https://brandplatform.annafreud.org/share/MXkddwvTwdABDnujqM2>

The Salppuri model of student participation in the Salpausselkä school in Lahti is underpinned by ongoing support of a dedicated youth worker and teacher working together.

<https://opinkirjo.fi/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/Salppurin-malli.pdf>

3.2 Voice

3.2.1 Forms of participation

Are young people engaged beyond consultation, e.g. through consultation to co-design or co-production of activities?

The Ministry of Education's Participatory Budget in Schools Scheme in Portugal allows young people to co-design and co-produce proposals for funding to improve their school environment. It is young people who also vote on the proposals to be selected for funding.

<https://opescolas.pt/videos/>

At Nervi–Severini Arts High School in Ravenna, youth voice is embedded in democratic procedures and decision making. Assemblies can be convened at the request of the student body, or its representatives, and resolutions are passed by open vote. Notable policies introduced as a result of this include a provision for menstrual leave.

<https://www.rainews.it/articoli/2022/12/un-liceo-artistico-di-ravenna-istituisce-il-congedo-mestruale-due-giorni-al-mese-e60fb010-6595-4081-8d69744b5052fe8e.html#:~:text=In%20particolare%20riconosce%20alle%20studentesse,la%20validit%C3%A0%20dell'anno%20scolastico>

Does participation include embodied and emotional modes of expression (e.g. storytelling, music, dance etc)?

The Radio Sonora project brings young participants together at workshops and events to imagine an urban regeneration project. They use dialogue and theatre to collectively design open and inclusive spaces.

<https://radiosonora.it/>

Barnardo's Children at the Table campaign called on the UK government to put children and young people at the heart of government policy making. The Charity uses drawing, stories and videos as means through which children and young people can express themselves and get their voices listened to.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=j05FMckx6Cw>

The PELE Urgent Youth – Here and Now project engaged with young people about politics and democracy in experimental ways. The young people used art, theatre, movement, dialogue and conversation to explore politics and the things that mattered to them in the here and now.

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-b4zb_AAXmY

The EC2U project organises interactive events - Makeathons - bringing together people and local organisations to collaboratively develop creative solutions to local challenges. In Poitiers, for example, this involved using street art as a means of expression to create an environment conducive to constructive dialogue and peace building.

https://ec2u.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/709/2024/06/RI4C2_WP5_D5_7_EC2U_Makeathon.pdf

Are digital technologies and social media employed to facilitate participation?

The Coletivo Matéria movement was created by a group of young people who published a manifesto demanding their ideas were heard by decision-makers. This led to the creation of a digital platform where young people could submit their ideas on how to resolve issues across a range of government policy areas. The group would then pass these on to policymakers and organise an event at which they can be discussed.

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSdRAqgPCzfAPUJfLfsgvPrGefrTuWXdH4euldCYNWdy9M7ifg/viewform>

The Authority for the Protection of Children and Adolescents in Italy uses regular online consultations to ensure that young people are heard. The questions included in these online surveys are written by young people, supported by experts. They have led to published reports on themes such as 'The school I would like' and 'The future I would like'.

<https://iopartecipo.garanteinfanzia.org/consultazioni-online/>

3.2.2 Sites of participation

Are young people able to participate in non-formal, everyday settings?

Turning Tables bases its 'culture labs' in the heart of under resourced urban areas to ensure local young people can access them. These projects empower children and young people and innovate Danish cultural life by allowing new voices in music, photography and film.

<https://www.turningtables.dk/vision>

The PELE Urgent Youth – Here and Now project organised several public events giving voice to and promoting young people's agency taking the form of presentations, occupations, performances, meetings, forums and assemblies.

<https://www.apele.org/pt/projetos-em-curso/jovens-urgentes-aqui-e-agora/>

If young people participate in formal sites, do these include places that would otherwise be hard for them to access (e.g. parliament)?

The WE DO Democracy Youth Citizens' Assembly was a formally organised process of random selection of a representative group of young people to work on developing youth-driven recommendations to the City of Copenhagen municipal authorities. Part of the process took place at formal premises, including the City Hall, and thus provided an important opportunity for young people to contribute to municipal political decision-making.

<https://www.wedodemocracy.dk/case/naar-unge-stemmer-til-kommunalvalget/>

3.2.3 Power and participation

Is participation always voluntary?

Leicester City Council sets out clearly what it considers good practice in youth participation. Its list of ten standards includes 'Choice', which is explained as: 'Young people should always have a choice whether they want to get involved in decision-making processes. This means knowing what a commitment involves and being able to make an informed decision.'

<https://consultations.leicester.gov.uk/communications/yp-participation/results/youngpeopleparticipationstrategy.pdf>

Is participation young person-led or young person-initiated?

The Listen Up! Campaign was designed and led by working-class young people aged 14-17 to get local government to listen to young people. It produced a Greater Manchester Youth Manifesto for Change and called on candidates for the upcoming Mayoral election to deliver on their proposals.

<https://www.reclaim.org.uk/listen-up>

Korso Complains is an impressive example of students at Ruusuvuori school in Vantaa taking the initiative to bring about change they see as necessary. For example, they launched a campaign against the Helsinki Regional Transport Authority's (HSL) intention to start charging for travel for school groups. The Korso Complains group organised a petition and wrote a letter of complaint to HSL, eventually securing a reversal of its decision. The group won an award from the Board of Education for its activity and is recognised by the Finnish National Agency for Education as a good practice.

<https://sites.google.com/view/korsovalittaa/etusivu>

Are young people able to set the agenda by bringing their issues into discussion?

Modstrøm is a student-led initiative to build active student councils across the Danish Preparatory Basic Education (FGU) school sector. The process starts with a listening exercise on any issue raised through the association's workshop and youth council. The findings must then be acted upon. One such exercise led to a letter being written to FGU directors requesting free student cards be provided at all FGU schools.

<https://xn--viermodstrm-pgb.dk/index.php/elevraadsunivers/>

Science Engagement to Empower aDoleScents (SEEDS) is a science project by teenagers for teenagers in schools in Spain, the Netherlands, Greece and the UK. It uses the principles of citizen science to promote healthy lifestyles through a series of Makeathon events. The interventions are co-created by the teenagers and allow them to explore how important and exciting science can be.

<https://www.ecsa.ngo/cases/seeds-science-engagement-to-empower-adolescents-2/>

The Students'Voice@DGE is an initiative of the Portuguese National Directorate of Education. Students in participating schools get the space to take a critical look at their environment and make proposals for changes that can make a positive difference to their everyday lives in school. Student representatives are able to participate in the monthly meetings of the Directorate of Education, where they can present the results of their work and concrete suggestions for changes

<https://www.dge.mec.pt/noticias/voz-dos-alunosdge>

Are young people seen as political actors or citizens in their own right?

Ungdomsøen is a physical island in the Copenhagen harbour, which was purchased by the Nordea Foundation and the A.P. Møller Foundation as a gift to all Danish youth. The island council is the chief decision-making body for the island and comprises of young people only. It is thus effectively youth led and promotes a 'youth as citizens' approach.

<https://ungdomsoen.dk/vision>

If activities are primarily about training for participation, are young people empowered to see themselves as citizens now, not just in the future?

The Danish Youth Council's 'Democracy Day' has been running since 2017. It brings workshops on democratic dialogue and panel discussions with politicians to up to 50 vocational schools annually. It is essentially aimed at equipping groups of young people who seldom participate in politics with the skills to do so. It is also peer-led.

<https://duf.dk/demokratietsdag>

3.2.4 Facilitating discussion and deliberation

Are a wide range of voices heard?

Escola da Ponte is a non-traditional school in Portugal, which uses autonomous and project learning to emphasise values of democracy, solidarity, respect for diversity and autonomy in its approach to learning. Students are invited to exercise their skills of argumentation, as an autonomous means of active citizenship through the School Assembly. All students are members of the Assembly which meets weekly to allow space for students to reflect and discuss issues of concern and present proposals for change in the school.

<https://www.escoladaponte.pt/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/Dispositivos->

Are facilitators or moderators employed to ensure equality in participation and/or mutual respect?

Lohikoski school in Jyväskylä has piloted an experimental form of class council for Finnish schools. It includes all students in deliberative decision-making at the class level and allows them to co-design and consult on weekly teaching plans as well as addressing a wide range of school-related issues (e.g. class practices, educational questions and interpersonal conflicts).

<https://opinkirjo.fi/luokkavaltuusto/>

The UPLIFT project aimed to focus young people's voices on addressing inequalities in 16 urban areas across Europe. It employed empathetic moderation, pairing and small group work as well as live polling platforms to ensure interactive discussion where everyone had the opportunity to express their opinion.

<https://uplift-youth.b-cdn.net/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/D4.8-Guidebook-on-RPA.pdf>

Are participants encouraged to develop a shared understanding of a social phenomenon as problematic or unjust?

The Our Life Our Voice Erasmus+ project allowed young people to use participatory methods to understand, and help find solutions to, youth poverty. In Romania, the practice encouraged young people to develop a shared understanding of the discrimination facing the Roma people and its effects on their lives.

https://ourlifeourvoice.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/Docs_Project/documents/InvestigationIntoPoverty.YP.IO1.pdf.pdf

3.3 Critique

3.3.1 Exposing and challenging power relations

Does the practice make visible and challenge structural power relations? E.g. does it expose and critique racialised, postcolonial, gendered, classed, heteronormative, ability-centred or age-centred norms that sustain existing hierarchies of power?

The Patto di collaborazione LGBTQIA+ Bologna drew up a General Covenant of Collaboration for the Promotion and Protection of the Rights of LGBTQIA+ people. It called for stronger intergenerational and intersectional collaborations to support non-binary people, particularly those affected by social loneliness and lack of family support networks. The proposed changes also advocated for utilising data more effectively to promote more inclusive policies and services capable of identifying and addressing 'multiple discrimination' facing LGBTQIA+ people.

https://www.comune.bologna.it/myportal/C_A944/api/content/download?id=63d28850f62634009700bdcc

Is the interwoven nature of structures of power recognised?

Youth Focus North West has dedicated, youth-friendly, resource packs on topics such as anti-racism, feminism and identity. These packs address the different forms of inequality and how they intersect. The origins of the concept of intersectionality in black feminism is outlined and the term is explained as being used to acknowledge a person's range of social identities (e.g. gender, race, sexuality, etc.). It states that intersectionality identifies advantages and disadvantages that are felt by people due to a combination of factors. Types of prejudice such as sexism or racism are recognised as not always existing in isolation but often combining to form a new type of oppression.

<https://youthfocusnw.org.uk/resource-centre>

3.3.2 Extending political agency

Is there sensitivity to the complexity of young people's identities?

The 'Multiple Voices' project run by the Youth Bureau in Denmark, published a collection of novels giving voice to young people's experiences of being in difficult situations such as being a refugee, suffering from a chronic disease or dropping out of education. These books not only gave young people a voice to express their stories, but also helped build awareness and appreciation of such experiences.

<https://ungdomsbureauet.dk/mangfoldigt-engagement/de-serien/>

The SALTO Youth Participation Strategy recognises that young people are not a homogenous group. It states that whilst they share many common experiences as a result of being part of the same generation, their lives are also intersected by gender, geography, sexuality, ethnicity and many other factors. This means that key concerns may differ among different groups and that there is not necessarily a single 'youth view' on an issue.

https://participationpool.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/ParticipationStrategy_SinglePage_Online_EN.pdf

Is there awareness that different identity factors may compound the exclusion of some young people?

Community Lab in Emilia-Romagna region, Italy, brings together schools, municipalities and healthcare organisations to empower young people and generate innovative welfare policies for young people. It notes the importance of being aware of the heterogeneity of the youth population and that interventions intended to foster participation must be appropriate for the very different experiences young people might have.

<https://salute.regione.emilia-romagna.it/prp/notizie/i-risultati-di-201c-community-lab-2022-2023-promozione-della-salute-in-eta-evolutiva201d>

The YES (Youth Engagement in Society) Erasmus+ project focused on increasing social inclusion and promoting active citizenship among young people who are not in education, employment or training. One activity it used was the 'Step forward game', which asks people to step forward, or stay put, based on whether they have a particular characteristic. This activity helps recognise and acknowledge the privileges and disadvantages participants share. It can be used to make visible existing power structures and mechanisms of marginalisation.

<https://projectserasmus.wixsite.com/yesproject/training-programme>

Does the practice actively encourage learning from people in marginalised positions?

In its Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Objectives, the Co-op Academy Belle Vue makes explicit the importance of peer learning from those with different experiences by ensuring those with different characteristics are represented and have a voice. The school aims to prepare pupils for life in a diverse society by encouraging respect for linguistic, cultural and religious diversity that exists in local communities and the wider world.

<https://www.coopacademies.co.uk/googledrive/?title=Equality+Diversity+%26+Inclusion+Policy+%282024%29&pid=0&gdfid=1wwzUHF7CWaW2H0E70t64EhzDDyL5QJSiF6TEjV8G9HU>

Is the contribution of a broader and more diverse range of participants recognised as vital to improving democracy?

The Changemaker! project worked with young people who had recently arrived in Finland to produce a Democracy Education Guide. The Guide recognises the additional support these young people need to develop the language skills, knowledge and confidence to become active citizens. The practice starts from the understanding that this targeted support is not only beneficial for the young migrants but that Finnish democracy will be enriched through more inclusive youth participation.

<https://plan.fi/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/Demokratiakasvatuksen-reittiopas-2022.pdf>

The 'Out of the box' initiative of the Danish Youth Refugee Council aims to increase and diversify representation of young people with a refugee background in public debate. They promote participation beyond the ballot box and work with creative expression and alternative forms of engagement to ensure democratic dialogue is accessible to a wider range of young people.

<https://stemmerudafboksen.dk/om/>

The Jovens na Política project views widening the social base of political participation as important for improving democracy. In particular, one initiative promoted under its 'Come on, get off the couch' campaign, sought to engage young people, including some from migrant and minority ethnic backgrounds, in discussion on topics related to young people's political participation, gender discrimination and racism.

<https://www.publico.pt/2021/09/14/p3/noticia/ques-discutir-politica-sai-sofa-ha-conversa-jovens-jovens-1976760>

3.3.3 Institutional Change

Does the practice aim to bring about institutional changes in public, political institutions or schools and organisations?

Youth PB Accelerator is an Erasmus+ project which sought to empower young people focusing on their participation in municipal participatory budgeting. This practice is designed for use in schools and colleges but also applicable to wider community spaces. Its institutional change lies in the requirement to share the resources or budgets of institutions with young people.

https://youthpb.eu/toolkit_english_pdf

Are the limits of deliberation, without structural change, recognised?

The Designing Dialogue project in Faro, produced a manifesto for change resulting from a series of youth participatory activities. The project not only promoted active citizenship and leadership among young people but also created opportunities for reflection on their participation in society, identifying existing obstacles, recommending solutions and promoting dialogue between young people and political decision-makers.

<https://contextos.org.pt/projectos/designing-dialogue/>

3.3.4 Challenging injustice

Does the practice aim to challenge injustice?

Politico Poetico is a theatre and active citizenship project working with secondary schools in Bologna. Its participants wrote a collective 'letter to the city' pointing out the deep inequalities that characterise everyday life. It calls on the city to recognise, and fight, the discrimination, exclusion and violence being faced by a range of young people due to disability, sexuality or migrant background.

https://static.teatrodelargine.org/Materiali_progetti/Le_cinque_Lettere_alla_Citt%C3%83%C2%A0_PP_agg_DEF.pdf

Climate Strike (Fridays for Future) is an example of a global youth-led movement where participation in protests, rallies and strikes fosters a shared understanding of the urgency of climate action. The movement recognises that the destruction caused by global warming will impact everyone but will be most devastating to the most vulnerable, namely, the poorest and youngest people.

<https://participedia.net/case/6100>

3.4 Recognition

3.4.1 Acknowledgment

Is participation publicly acknowledged?

Participation People delivers youth engagement projects to help businesses and organisations listen to young people's voices. It has a publicly available, user-friendly policy document setting out the difference between incentives, recognition and reward and providing a template for planning how they can be embedded in projects and activities. It states that not only should the valuable contribution of children and young people be acknowledged but young people should be involved in designing how incentives, rewards and recognition are given.

https://participationpeople.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/PP-_-Young-People-Incentives-POLICY-2020-Compressed.pdf

Is young people's voice accorded respect?

Emilia-Romagna Region's youth forum (YOUZ) was designed to include young people – including those in rural communities - in the co-design of future regional policies. The practice recognises the particular qualities - including empathy, sensitivity, taking a stand and supporting those in need - and skills that young people bring. It also noted that their participation had been indispensable in creating an innovative, inclusive and participatory vision for the transformation of the Inner and Mountainous Areas of Emilia Romagna and the construction of a sustainable and prosperous future.

<https://www.giovozooemr.it/it/partecipazione/youz/>

3.4.2 Reward

Is participation remunerated (paid)?

Seven members, their deputies, and a maximum of five experts are appointed to the Sámi Youth Council for a term of 2 years. Participation in Youth Council meetings is paid at €60 for members and €80 for the Chair.

https://dokumentit.solinum.fi/samediggi/download/?d=dokumenttipankki/kokousasiakirjat/saamelaisk%C3%A4r%C3%A4jien_kokous/toimikausi_2020-2023/kokouskutsut_ja_esityslistat/suomeksi/sakahel22021_liite_6_saka_palkkios%C3%A4%C3%A4nt%C3%B6.pdf

Participation People's Young People Incentives policy states that children and young people should be paid when asked to undertake a task beyond the expectation of a volunteer role. The organisation pays 'Young Consultants' at subject area experts' rates.

<https://participationpeople.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/PP-Young-People-Incentives-POLICY-2020-Compressed.pdf>

Is participation recognised in a non-monetary way (e.g. accreditation, certification, awards, publicity)?

The RE:ACT project organised by Rapolitics conducted 100 rap workshops at schools across Denmark. Ten of the schools went on to be included in a podcast released on Spotify. The project also brought together an audience of over 5,000 young people at the Roskilde Festival (2024) where acts included young rappers from the workshops.

<https://www.rapolitics.dk/projekter/re-act>

Salpausselkä school in Lahti adopts the Salppuri student council model. As part of this, the work done by young people is made visible through thank-you and award ceremonies where young people come together in a relaxed and informal manner, eat together and remember and evaluate the activities undertaken.

<https://opinkirjo.fi/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/Salppurin-malli.pdf>

Do participants gain expert knowledge or training during the practice? If so, is this knowledge or skill accredited or certified?

Bytes runs programmes that support young people in Northern Ireland who are furthest from opportunity. Participants have achieved a range of qualifications through a hybrid learning model, which combines one-to-one sessions, group work and online learning. It also runs programmes on digital skills and supporting young people to improve their own financial literacy and use their skills to support increased digital and financial literacy in others.

<https://www.bytes.org/programmes/>

3.5. Impact

3.5.1 Impact objectives

Does young people's voice contribute to decision making?

The EU Youth Dialogue is mechanism for dialogue between young people and decision makers as part of the EU Youth Strategy. The conclusions from the Youth dialogue activities are presented to the Council of the European Union, which may then adopt a policy document reflecting the views of young people.

https://youth.europa.eu/get-involved/eu-youth-dialogue/what-eu-youth-dialogue_en

In Santa Maria da Feira, the person elected as the municipality's Young Mayor has their own budget to allow them to implement actions in the community.

<https://files.diariodarepublica.pt/2s/2018/01/007000000/0116701170.pdf>

Are explicit recommendations made in order to achieve policy impact?

The DEEP-linking YOUTH project produced a set of nine recommendations for improving learning mobility programmes (such as the ERASMUS programme). These were generated by improving communication between young people and stakeholders, politicians, and organisations by linking them through the Digital Dashboard created by the project.

<https://ecas.org/learning-mobility-recommendations/>

MyPolis is a digital democracy platform, providing tools and resources to help young people shape their ideas and submit proposals for changes in their community. Young people submit their own proposals to the platform and vote on those to be taken forward. The organisation then works with municipalities to help ensure selected proposals are implemented.

<https://www.mypolis.eu/pt>

In the Free High School, Denmark, democratic governance is rooted in the student assembly, which has broad powers to influence all aspects of school life from budgets and curriculum to food served in the canteen. This is documented in the minutes from the monthly meetings.

<https://www.detfri.dk/generelt/en-demokratisk-skole/regler/>

3.5.2 Stated impact

Are the impacts of policy recommendations, projects or activities made public?

Through the Helsinki Youth Initiative, any Helsinki resident aged 13-17 can submit an initiative to the city council. Twice a year, initiatives received from young people are referred to the city council and all receive a response. The initiatives, and their responses, are published on the Youth Helsinki website.

<https://nuorten.hel.fi/aloitteet/>

Are concrete examples or case studies of how young people's voice is listened to made public?

The Youth Combined Authority in the Greater Manchester city region has a clear set of guidelines for monitoring outcomes to ensure youth voice and participation make a measurable difference to children and young people, services and communities. Evidence that this is achieved is detailed through concrete case studies such as the introduction of the free bus travel card for young people in the region.

<https://www.greatermanchester-ca.gov.uk/what-we-do/equalities/youth-combined-authority/>

3.5.3 Monitoring and assessing impact

Is there a system for monitoring and evidencing impact of the practice?

Young people's mental health charity Anna Freud has Champions' panels and 'huddles' as well as Ambassadors' groups and a Participation Steering Group that work at project and organisation level to ensure a constant process of monitoring how young people's voice is being heard, by whom and with what impact. It publishes participation blogs by young people and gives best practice examples on its website.

<https://www.annafreud.org/participation/>

The Xing-Crossing project published details of activities implemented and the numbers of people participating. It also provided evidence that the young people's council was directly included in the process that led to the Pact of Common Goods for an anti-racist Turin. This monitoring of impact is part of a commitment of the organisation to ensure that change is realised not only in the lives of those participating but for wider society.

<https://www.programmaintegra.it/wp/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/XING-report-finale-22-6-2021.pdf>

Is the impact resulting from participation fed back to young people?

Feedback is a key element Somerset Council's youth participation model. It states that participation does not simply mean 'taking part' but as having some influence over decisions and action. The Council commits to informing young people of how their involvement has been used, and the outcomes, so they can see the difference their involvement has made.

<https://www.somerset.gov.uk/children-families-and-education/the-local-offer/talking-to-people-finding-support/somerset-participation-toolkit/>

A neighbourhood school renovation project in Bologna makes public the details of all its activities. The ideas of the young people participating were showcased in a festival open to the public. A final report detailing the results of the process, the experimental activities and the joint planning session with the municipality was drawn up and will guide future educational policies

<https://scuolediquartiere.bo.it/>

Has the practice or project been formally assessed and its results made public?

The YouCount project undertook an impact assessment of its practices. It noted that it was too early to assess the societal impact, through policymaking, of the project. However, the assessment revealed some immediate impacts related to the project itself and to the lives of the young people who engaged in the practice as co-creators. These included the acknowledgement of young people's work and leadership in the research process; the establishment of a more democratic process for decision-making (within the project); and positive changes in relational dynamics connected with equality and new gender roles.

<https://www.youcountproject.eu/resources/project-reports>

Is learning from the assessment detailed?

The Participatory Budget in Schools project, implemented by the Portuguese Ministry of Education provides participating schools with an official channel (General Inspectorate of Education and Science) to which they can present any complaints that they may have regarding the selection and implementation processes of the school actions selected for support.

<https://files.diariodarepublica.pt/2s/2017/01/005000001/0000200004.pdf>

4. CONCLUSION

The key findings of the critical assessments of youth deliberative and participatory practices at EU-level (Huttunen et al. 2024) and at national and local levels (Mirshak and Pilkington, 2024) conducted within the framework of the SINCRONY project are used to develop an integrated set of criteria to identify good practice. The inclusion of a wide range of cases - 20 EU-level projects as well as 25 educational and 50 organisational settings across five European countries - in the initial analyses, makes this integrated set of criteria suitable for use across different national settings, types of organisations and educational settings.

In establishing a single list of criteria, a key critical reflection was that the criteria should avoid academic or policy jargon and be designed to facilitate assessment of the substance rather than description of practices. Thus, while seeking to highlight a practice's attention to inclusivity and intersectionality, the criteria should capture practices that recognise, and work to tackle, inequalities arising from overlapping identities rather than only practices which articulate this through the language of intersectional inequality.

These integrated criteria were then applied to the 95 cases and examples of good practice for each of the criteria and sub-criteria were identified. In total the report includes 82 examples of good practice in relation to these criteria. It should be noted that many more examples were identified among the cases studied. The examples included in the report have been selected, therefore, with the aim of including as wide a range as possible in terms of the sector, level (EU, national, local), type of project or organisation and national context. Many of the cases analysed could have been cited under multiple criteria as good practice; it was also a conscious choice that no individual case would be cited more than twice. This was to avoid skewing the examples given towards any particular type of organisation, setting or national context and illustrating the many different ways in which good practice is achieved. The number of examples cited under each criterion varies. This reflects a relative paucity of available documentation on some criteria (for example recruitment of young people or evaluation or assessment of projects) which does not necessarily imply that good practice on this is not evident, it is just not documented publicly.

All examples of good practice are accompanied by a publicly available source for further information. The links given are, where possible, to English language websites or documents. However, examples of good practice where information is available only in the local language are also included. These sources provide much more detail about the practices themselves and the contexts in which they have been used and readers are strongly encouraged to explore these resources further.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to acknowledge the work to amplify youth voices being undertaken by all the organisations, local authorities and schools and colleges cited here. As we are citing good practice of these organisations we have chosen to name them. All information cited is publicly available.

These good practices were identified initially by partner teams in participating countries (Denmark, Finland, Italy, Portugal and the UK) and the full national level analyses are published as or available upon request from:

Albanesi, C. (2024) *Mapping and analysing community and local level practices: National Report Italy*, SINCRONY Project D3.2 - Deliverable Report on the analysis of national and local DPPs.

Bruselius-Jensen. M & Dånge. L. (2024) *Mapping and analysing community and local level practices: National Report Denmark*, SINCRONY Project D3.2 - Deliverable Report on the analysis of national and local DPPs.

Korventausta, M. and Huttunen, J. (2024) *Mapping and analysing community and local level practices in Finland*, SINCRONY Project D3.2 - Deliverable Report on the analysis of national and local DPPs.

Mirshak, N. and Pilkington, H. (2024) *Mapping and analysing community and local level practices in the UK*, SINCRONY Project D3.2 – Deliverable Report on the analysis of national and local DPPs.

Piedade, F., Malafaia, C., Ferreira, P., Pais, S., Menezes, I. and Marques da Silva, S. (2024) *Mapping and analysing community and local level practices: Portuguese National Report*, SINCRONY Project D3.2 - Deliverable Report on the analysis of national and local DPPs.

6. REFERENCES

Huttunen, J., Korventausta, M., Leino, M. & Setälä, M. (2024) *Assessment of EU-level deliberative and participatory practices through an intersectional lens*, SINCRONY Deliverable Report 3.1

Mirshak, N. and Pilkington, H. (2024) *Analysis of National and Local Deliberative and Participatory Practices*, SINCRONY Deliverable Report 3.2.